

Pyrexia of Unknown Origin Caused by Toxoplasmosis: A Rare Case Report

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Abstract

Introduction: *Toxoplasma gondii* is an obligate intracellular parasite that causes infection in up to one-third of the world's population. It is essential to document every such case for the education of the clinicians for better treatment of the affected individuals. **Case presentation:** We present a 50-year-old individual of Bangladeshi lineage who presented as pyrexia of unknown origin who was ultimately diagnosed as acute Toxoplasmosis. The patient was treated conservatively with a range of antibiotics, he gradually became clinically and hemodynamically stable and was released. **Conclusion:** The case highlights the importance of extensive diagnostic measures for assessing the actual cause of the disease, as the presentation will be mostly non-specific. Such cases enhance the knowledge of the practitioners for implying proper diagnosis and offering effective treatment to the patients.

Introduction

Toxoplasmosis, prevalent worldwide, is a zoonotic infection caused by the intracellular parasite *Toxoplasma gondii*. [1] Despite its global reach, it rarely causes clinically significant disease in immunocompetent individuals; usually asymptomatic; occasionally presenting with nonspecific, constitutional symptoms, such as fever, malaise and lymphadenopathy. Due to the unexposed nature of the condition, the physicians are not well aware of its clinical presentation; hence the disease burden is underestimated. [2] However, the disease exhibits its true appearance in immunocompromised persons, such as those with chronic diseases, receiving chemotherapy, or those infected with HIV/AIDS, causing life-threatening infection. [2] It often presents as pyrexia of unknown origin (PUO), making it more complicated to come under the light of diagnosis as they have already surpassed the baseline investigations. [3] Such evaluation requires a holistic approach to conclude the actual diagnosis of the

patient. The following report elaborates a unique case of an immunosuppressed individual who had developed this rare entity. Reporting every single case and publishing it would be highly beneficial in terms of accumulating valid information and offering comprehensive efforts for the optimum management of this disease condition.

Description of the Case

A 50-year-old male, truck driver by profession, smoker, hailing from Dhaka was admitted in the Department of Medicine, Bangladesh Specialized Hospital situated in Dhaka, Bangladesh. The gentleman, previously diagnosed with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus and heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF). He was brought to the hospital with the complaints of fever with chills and rigor, with the highest recorded temperature being 104°F; along with increased frequency of urination and generalized weakness for the last 15 days; nausea and loss of appetite for the last 7 days; and vomiting episodes on several occasions for the last 4 days. He had not travelled recently, nor had

he had any recent contact with sick people. However, upon extensive enquiry of the patient, it was discovered that he used to rear chickens in his house for the last couple of years. It was also evaluated that he had no diagnosed hypertension or any other comorbidities besides the ones mentioned above. On examination, his temperature was 102°F; SpO₂: 97%; other vitals and blood glucose level on glucometer reading appeared normal. After the general and systemic examination of the patient was completed, which did not reveal any abnormalities, all sorts of relevant investigations were performed to evaluate the actual cause of his fever. Noteworthy findings included white blood cell count: 13,000/ μ L; C-Reactive protein: 117.7 mg/dL; ESR: 87 mm/hr, urinary pus cells: 6-10/HPF, throat swab for Gram stain: few Gram-positive cocci; serum alkaline phosphatase: 543 IU/L; Toxoplasma IgM: 14.82 AU/mL; Toxoplasma IgG: 28.72 AU/mL. Other investigations including fasting blood sugar, serum electrolytes, serum creatinine, urine for C/S, screening for other TORCH infections, lipid profile, COVID-19 rapid antigen test, Mantoux test, Widal test and so on were all normal. Chest X-Ray, ultrasound of whole abdomen and echocardiography were also done and did not reveal any major abnormalities.

Figure 1: Chest X-ray P/A View of the Patient Suggesting Normal Findings

After confirmation of the diagnosis, patient received conservative management. He was administered with Inj. Piperacillin + Tazobactam (4.5 gm), Inj. Azithromycin (500 mg), Inj. Moxifloxacin (400 mg), Inj. Meropenem (1 gm) for the treatment of Toxoplasmosis and urinary tract infection. Furthermore, Tab. Cotrimoxazole (960 mg) was also given to the patient on the 6th day of hospitalization. The patient gradually became afebrile after 8 days of treatment;

improvement of his overall condition was observed and after 10 days, he was discharged from the hospital. He was advised about the rules for handling poultry such as maintenance of adequate hand hygiene and washing all surfaces which come in contact with it.

Figure 2: 2D-Echocardiography of the Patient. No Regional Wall Abnormality Present, Good LV Systolic and Diastolic Function (LVEF=67%), Good RV Systolic Function

Figure 3 (a) and (b): Temperature Chart of the Patient. It is Clear that, from the Start of Hospitalization, the Temperature was Seen to Fluctuate from Baseline to High Temperature. From 7th November, the Temperature was Found to be in the Normal Range

The patient was regularly seen at outpatient clinic after his discharge from hospital, His condition gradually improved, without a return of complaints or fever. The patient remained seropositive (IgM and IgG) during six months of follow-up.

The patient was regularly seen for follow-up at our outpatient clinic after his discharge. His condition had improved, without a return of previous complaints. The patient remained seropositive (IgM and IgG) during six months of follow-up.

Discussion

People can become infected with *T. gondii* by accidental ingestion of tissue cysts in the undercooked meat of intermediate hosts, particularly pork and lamb; or by the ingestion of food or water contaminated by feces which contain oocysts from the definitive host, members of the feline family; or transplacental infection of the fetus; white blood cell transfusion or organ transplantation. [4] Our patient was possibly infected by the chickens he reared; most likely, proper hygiene measures like using gloves or washing hands on regular basis were not maintained.

Previous case reports have conveyed the message that the disease has a greater prevalence among men (79.0% against 63.4% in women) and that age-dependent seroprevalence reached a value of more than 92% in the age range of 40 to 50 years. [5]

Differential diagnosis of PUO includes a diverse list, starting from bacterial infections such as Q fever or brucellosis; viral infections such as Epstein-Barr virus or cytomegalovirus; parasitic infections such as malaria or toxoplasmosis; fungal infections such as histoplasmosis; inflammatory conditions such as systemic lupus erythematosus or polyarteritis nodosa; neoplasms such as non-Hodgkin's lymphoma or leukemia; or miscellaneous such as drugs or sarcoidosis, to name a few. [3] Our case presented with long-standing and undiagnosed fever along with certain constitutional symptoms. Since the individual was diabetic, smoker, a case of HFpEF, we can fairly say that he was somewhat immunocompromised. Literature reveals various complications of Toxoplasmosis in immunocompromised individuals, such as chorioretinitis, pneumonitis, encephalitis or multi-organ failure. [2,4] Fortunately, the patient was brought to the hospital and managed accordingly which avoided the chances of acquiring such adversities.

Though the disease was addressed as PUO and extensive tests were performed; the preferred mode of diagnosis for Toxoplasmosis is serological evaluation (IgM and IgG for *T. gondii*). [6] Our case also received the ultimate diagnosis with the help of serological tests, supported by leukocytosis, raised CRP levels and ESR. In addition, the patient also suffered from urinary tract infection, as confirmed by the routine microscopic urinary examination despite having normal urinary C/S.

Our case was treated with 5 antibiotics overall, namely Inj. Piperacillin + Tazobactam (4.5 gm), Inj. Azithromycin (500 mg), Tab. Cotrimoxazole (960 mg), Inj. Moxifloxacin (400 mg), Inj. Meropenem (1 gm) focusing on both Toxoplasma as well as urinary tract infection. On the contrary, according to studies, treatment of choice has been combination of pyrimethamine and clindamycin. [6] Although some studies also suggest that prophylactic treatment with trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, along with the empiric therapy are often indicated for immunosuppressed individuals to improve outcomes. [2] Some studies also mention that, pyrimethamine, sulfadiazine and folic acid are the preferred treatment for immunocompromised individuals or those who have a strong immune system but the symptoms are severe or persistent. [7]

The prognosis is favorable in terms of immunocompetent individuals; however, proper treatment must be ensured in case of immunocompromised patients in order to avoid unwanted consequences.

Toxoplasmosis is a growing public health concern in Bangladesh even in urban societies owing to growing pet ownership trends. Public health initiatives, such as awareness campaigns, seminars and educational workshops, especially among pet and poultry owners are empirical to prevent the spread of this disease and protect sensitive populations, for instance, pregnant women and those with weakened immune systems.

Conclusion

Timely diagnosis and accurate treatment are essential to ensure proper recovery and combat the negative consequences of the otherwise serious infection. Measures such as safe food handling practices, avoidance of undercooked meat consumption, implementing hand hygiene rules, incorporating prenatal screening and educating pet owners are some of the strategies that can be used to minimize the potential of the disease. More research is required to comprehend the true burden of Toxoplasmosis in Bangladesh.

Conflict of Interest

None declared.

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